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Research Article

**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND AWARENESS ABOUT
VARIOUS POSSIBLE TREATMENT THERAPIES AMONG
PATIENTS ABOUT PROSTHODONTIC TREATMENT**

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Abstract:

We carried out this research in order to estimate the knowledge, awareness and attitude of the patients towards various treatment options available for prosthodontic treatment. Information about the response of patients was collected through a self-administered questionnaire at Services Hospital, Lahore (October 2017 to April 2018). The primary focus of the questions was to assess the preferable methods of missing tooth replacement. The research population was selected in the age bracket of (14 – 77) years. Every patient was partially edentulous with the exception of third molars. Among 201 patients' males were 114 and females were 87. Outcomes were analyzed through SPSS software. The researcher also computed descriptive statistics for this research. Outcomes presented various levels of awareness about different treatment options such as fixed partial denture (45%), acrylic removable partial denture (26%), cast partial denture (17%) and implants (4%). Awareness level about the missing teeth was much lower than other options. Therefore, it is important to inculcate the importance of different dental prosthesis among those patients who need their missing teeth replaced. The role of oral healthcare providers is very much important in this whole situation.

Keywords: *Knowledge, Attitude, Awareness, Missing Teeth, Prosthodontic and Treatment Options.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral health is of extreme importance as oral complications can lead to reduced concentrations on regular routine and hindrance in the ability of an individual. Among various dental care issues, the loss of tooth causes distress and also affects life quality [1]. Various factors are involved in missing tooth replacement through the dental prosthesis. In these factors, the most important factor is of the dental prosthesis [2].

In the broader perspective, there are two main categories of prosthodontics treatment which include fixed and removable prosthesis. An improved state of awareness about the prosthodontic treatment surely helps in the selection of appropriate dental treatment [3]. The functional comfort and aesthetics are also necessary and important for the selection of dental prosthesis and also for the anterior replacement as more important in comparison to the posterior teeth [4].

Other factors like socioeconomic status, gender, age, missing tooth count etc. are also equally important for the appropriate dental prosthesis selection. Patients of a young age are more interested in the implant supported prosthesis than a traditional prosthesis. Most of the females show their interest in tooth replacement at the earliest as they are more concerned about esthetics [5].

It is important for the prosthodontist to know the feeling of patients and provide adequate information which clearly reflects reality. This will assist in the fulfilling of patient's expectations about desired outcomes. Without having access to accurate and current information chances of misguidance are also prevalent through industry and media. Such information is not always true to completely reveal the facts [6].

Media is a vibrant source to mould and modify the perceptions of general masses in some of the

countries; whereas, among other countries the only source about dental healthcare are dentists. However, a number of cultural and social attitudes, influences and beliefs also determine the acceptance of patients about prosthodontic treatment-related esthetic aspects [7].

We carried out this research in order to estimate the knowledge, awareness and attitude of the patients towards various treatment options available for prosthodontic treatment.

METHODOLOGY:

We carried out this research in order to estimate the knowledge, awareness and attitude of the patients towards various treatment options available for prosthodontic treatment. Information about the response of patients was collected through a self-administered questionnaire at Services Hospital, Lahore (October 2017 to April 2018). The primary focus of the questions was to assess the preferable methods of missing tooth replacement. The research population was selected in the age bracket of (14 – 77) years. Every patient was partially edentulous with the exception of third molars. Among 201 patients' males were 114 and females were 87. Outcomes were analyzed through SPSS software. The researcher also computed descriptive statistics for this research.

RESULTS:

The proportion of various treatment options among males and females in terms of selection and rejection is given in the tabular and graphical form below. It reflects among males the respective acceptance of treatment as FIX PD (55%), REM PD (46%), IMPLANT (9%) and CPD (11%); whereas, the rejection of the treatment options as FIX PD (59%), REM PD (68%), IMPLANT (105%) and CPD (76%). Among females the respective acceptance of treatment as FIX PD (67%), REM PD (63%), IMPLANT (2%) and CPD (35%); whereas, the rejection of the treatment options as FIX PD (20%), REM PD (24%), IMPLANT (85%) and CPD (79%).

Table: Awareness about various treatment options among males and females

Treatment Options		Yes	No
Male	FIX PD	55	59
	REM PD	46	68
	IMPLANT	9	105
	CPD	11	76
Female	FIX PD	67	20
	REM PD	63	24
	IMPLANT	2	85
	CPD	35	79

DISCUSSION:

General health is mostly affected by dental health. General health and psychological health are compromised with teeth loss. Missing teeth replacement is very much necessary on early basis to stop oral deterioration and general health condition [8].

Awareness and knowledge of the patients play an important role in the selection of suitable dental prosthesis. We can determine the awareness and knowledge level among patients in a number of ways. In this particular research, we used the self-designed questionnaire as an information collection tool. Rustemeyer also did the same in order to gather data about the awareness and knowledge of the dental prosthesis [9].

Other factors like socioeconomic status, gender, age, missing tooth count etc. are also equally important for the appropriate dental prosthesis selection. Patients of a young age are more interested in the implant supported prosthesis than a traditional prosthesis. Most of the females show their interest in tooth replacement at the earliest as they are more concerned about aesthetics. According to Abdurrahman, the awareness is better among young age groups than older age groups which are the same as we reported in this particular research.

Schützhold reported that socioeconomic background and educational level are also critical indicators to estimate the level of awareness among patients especially for the selection of appropriate dental prosthesis. Better awareness about dental prosthesis

was prevalent among more educated patients which are also the same as we reported in this particular research [11, 12].

Level of awareness and knowledge in this research showed that 77% of patients were aware of RPD. Among these patients, the proportion for the awareness about Cast partial dentures and acrylic dentures was respectively 22.8% and 54.2%. There was no patient who was aware of immediate denture.

A meagre percentage of 5.5% was reported about implant supported prosthesis which is not same as reported by various other scholars as Shah reported a higher onset of implant-supported prosthesis (41.7%) and another author reported the same as (70.1%) [13, 14].

Generally, outcomes of the research show different and reduced levels of knowledge and awareness among patients which required immediate and tangible steps to meet the challenge. Everyone including oral health care providers, family members, media and friends need to play their role in this regard [15].

Early replacement of missing teeth is only possible through education and awareness. This timely management of missing teeth will enhance the life quality of the patients [16].

CONCLUSION:

Patients were not satisfactorily aware of the possible missing teeth treatment options. The awareness level was very low among patients which requires more

emphasis on the education of different dental prosthesis among patients.

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